

Full Research Paper

Leveraging technology to enhance workability in the healthcare & welfare sector: A participatory Living Lab approach

Authors

Femke Drijkoningen¹, Vicky Van der Auwera¹, Leen Broeckx¹, Ingrid Adriaensen¹, Dr. Nele De Witte¹, Dr. Kim Helsen¹

¹ LiCalab – Living and Care Lab, Centre of Expertise Care and Well-being, Thomas More University of Applied Sciences, Geel, Belgium

Abstract

Care demands are rising and putting additional pressure on healthcare and welfare workers. Innovative methods and technologies could be essential to address current challenges. This study explores the role of technology in alleviating the challenges in various care sectors, including elderly care, disability care, youth care, childcare, and social enterprises for supported employment in Flanders. Through a participatory living lab approach, we engaged workers of these sectors in interviews ($n = 38$), co-creation ($n = 52$) and a survey ($n = 526$). They identified key challenges related to mental strain, physical strain, and work organization. These challenges were mapped into six categories of care technologies: activating care technology, assistive care technology, relaxing care technology, ergonomic care technology, administrative support tools, and educational support tools. Our findings suggest that these technologies can address these challenges by reducing mental and physical strain and improving work organization. Despite a general openness to technology, barriers such as cost, training, time constraints, and resistance to change were mentioned as obstacles for successful implementation. The study highlights the importance of a collaborative approach involving healthcare professionals and managers to ensure acceptance and effective integration of technology.

Key words

Care technology, Workability, Healthcare, Welfare, Living lab approach

Introduction

Challenges in the Healthcare and Welfare Sector

The demand for care is rising, driven primarily by demographic shifts such as population ageing and a growing number of chronically ill patients (Kroezen et al., 2015; Kingston, Comas-Herrera & Jagger, 2018). Citizens also have increasingly higher expectations regarding the quality and accessibility of care (Zorgnet Icuuro, 2024), yet studies highlight a gap between these expectations and actual care experiences, especially in communication and feeling respected (A'aqoulah, Kuyini, & Albalas, 2022; Freilich et al., 2019).

Internally, healthcare organizations face acute staff shortages, a challenge seen in Belgium and elsewhere (VDAB, 2024; Marc et al., 2018; Shemtob et al., 2023), worsened by an ageing workforce (Kroezen et al., 2015). This contributes to increased workload, lower job satisfaction, and compromised care quality. At the same time, care is becoming more technical and interdisciplinary, requiring continuous learning and effective team collaboration (Barber et al., 2023; Czypionka et al., 2020). Additionally, addressing emotional and psychological patient needs adds to the emotional strain on workers (Suh & Punnett, 2022). Emotional exhaustion is a serious issue among Belgian care providers, negatively impacting well-being, retention, and work capacity (Vandenbroeck et al., 2017). Key stressors include workload, emotional demands, role conflict, and work-home interference, while learning opportunities and support systems offer protection (Vandenbroeck et al., 2017). Job satisfaction, recognition, career development, and work-life balance are crucial for retention (Hudays et al., 2024; De Vries et al., 2023).

Overall, the "workability" of jobs in care is under pressure. According to the Social and Economic Council of Flanders (SERV; in the northern region of Belgium), it depends on mental strain, workplace well-being, learning opportunities, and work-life balance. Improving workability benefits both employees and employers through reduced absenteeism, higher motivation, and knowledge retention (SERV, 2024). Given limited resources, a shift toward preventive care is essential, though it alters job roles and organization (World Health Organization, 2016).

Technology as a Supportive Solution

Innovative methods and technologies are essential to address current challenges in healthcare and welfare. While their adoption can pose difficulties, technology also offers major opportunities to make work more workable by relieving workloads, enhancing skills,

and efficiently training new workers (Zorginstituut Nederland, 2024). Despite concerns about job loss (imec digimeter: De Marez, Georges, Sevenhant, & Devos, 2025), technology's role should be to support, not replace, care professionals.

Successful integration requires involving healthcare workers in the design and implementation process to foster acceptance and build knowledge, thereby strengthening organizational support (Turner et al., 2021). A user-centered, collaborative approach ensures that technologies meet both provider and patient needs, thereby improving workflows and ensuring long-term viability (Robertson, Brauer, Burton-Jones, Grimley, & Rosbergen, 2024). Recent research supports this, showing that engaging users not only enhances the relevance of technological solutions but also contributes to their adaptability and long-term sustainability (De Witte et al., 2025). Interoperability through standardized systems is also key to integrating technologies like AI effectively and efficiently (Saadat, 2025). Finally, continuous training is essential for the effective and sustainable use of new technologies in daily care (Garcia et al., 2024).

Aim of This Study

This study builds on the previously outlined challenges in healthcare and welfare and aims to examine how professionals in Flanders experience their work and what they feel is missing to improve their job quality, focusing on mental and physical well-being, and work organization.

Secondly, it investigates attitudes toward workplace technology, identifies potential tech solutions for (sector-specific) issues, and highlights the conditions needed for successful implementation. The research targets institutions in Flanders across elderly care, disability care, youth care, childcare, and social enterprises for supported employment (Figure 1), using a living lab methodology – an open, user-centered innovation model where stakeholders co-develop and test solutions in real-world environments. This ensures tech solutions are practical and aligned with actual workforce needs.

Figure 1. Targeted healthcare and welfare institutions

This study took place in the context of “Proeftuin Technologie voor Werkbaar Werk in Zorg en Welzijn”. It evaluates technologies that aim to make work in healthcare more workable, sustainable and rewarding. These innovations are tested in real-world settings across the involved sectors. The focus is on reducing work pressure and increasing job satisfaction for professionals, contributing to a more resilient and future-proof care sector. The project partners are imec, Flanders Make, Thomas More, PXL, and UCLL – three universities of applied sciences and two regional research institutes.

Methods

Procedure: Living Lab - Mixed Methods Research Design

Using a mixed-methods approach within a living lab framework, we explored the needs of workers in the different sectors. This iterative process combined qualitative and quantitative methods – semi-structured expert interviews, co-creation sessions, and an online survey (Figure 2) – with each method proving complementary and deeper insights, iteratively enriching the overall understanding of their challenges.

All participants signed an informed consent. Ethical approval for the survey was granted by SMEC at KU Leuven (G-2024 07 2208).

Figure 2. Phases of iteration in this study

Participants

Participants were recruited via personal email invitations sent through LiCalab's user panel, as well as through flyers and social media. Additional stakeholder groups were approached depending on the specific activity.

For expert interviews, recruitment focused on directors, HR, innovation managers, and other managers from the targeted sectors. In line with sample size recommendations (Carlsen & Glenton, 2011; Guest et al., 2017; Morse, 2000), the study aimed to include 30 participants for the interviews and host 3 to 5 co-creation sessions with 6 to 10 healthcare workers.

The online survey was open to all employees in the targeted sectors, covering diverse roles such as nurses, therapists, managers, social workers, and support workers. The only eligibility criteria were being 18 or older, working in one of the sectors, being based in Flanders or Brussels, and have sufficient proficiency in the Dutch language.

Materials and Instruments

Expert Interviews

An interview guide, based on the Flemish Workability Monitor (SERV, 2024), covered key risk factors (e.g., workload, emotional stress, autonomy) and workability indicators (e.g., mental fatigue, well-being, work-life balance). Current use, barriers, and the potential of workplace technologies were also explored. The semi-structured format allowed for both consistency and in-depth exploration. Most interviews (one hour each) were conducted online to reduce logistical barriers and began with an overview of the project and research objectives.

Co-Creation Sessions and Preparatory Diary

Co-creation sessions identified (1) energy-draining and energy-boosting factors, (2) sector-specific challenges, and (3) use, barriers, and the potential of workplace technologies. Sessions (two hours each) were held at partner locations and began with sector-specific brainstorming, followed by group discussion using idea generation, dot voting for prioritization, and a final individual form on current technologies and perceived benefits. Participants completed a five-day diary in advance, spending less than ten minutes per day reflecting on tasks, energy levels, and technology use, enhancing engagement.

Online Survey

The survey focused on mental and physical well-being, work organization, and attitudes toward technology, based on SERV (2024). Demographic questions allowed comparison with regional workforce data (Statbel, 2020). The survey consisted mainly of closed questions, with a few optional open-ended items for more explanation. Completion time was ca. 15 minutes. Scales and items were selected from validated questionnaires to ensure relevance while limiting survey length (Table 1). Reliability was generally good, however, the "variation" ($\alpha = 0.38$) and "ergonomics" ($\alpha = 0.07$) scales had low reliability, possibly due to item heterogeneity. For instance, the "variation" scale covered task complexity and skill variety, while "ergonomics" included seating, workspace adjustability, and physical demand

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

Table 1. Description of sources and adaptations for the questionnaire subscales and item

Theme	Subtheme	Instrument	Selected items or scales	Range and interpretation range	Cronbach's Alpha
Mental well-being	Workload	FNV Workload Quick scan (https://www.fnv.nl/werk-inkomen/veilig-gezond-werken/werkdruk)	Six items on <i>Experienced Workload</i>	6–24; higher scores indicate higher workload	0.88
	Emotional Demands	Knipperlichtmeter (Familiezorg, 2008)	Scale <i>Work-Pressure</i>	4–20; lower scores indicate higher emotional demands	0.56
	Task Variety	Work Design Questionnaire (Morgeson & Humphrey, 2006)	One item on <i>Task Variety</i> , two items on <i>Task Complexity</i> , two items on <i>Problem-Solving</i> , two items on <i>Skill Variety</i>	7–35; higher scores indicate more task variety	0.38
	Autonomy	Work Design Questionnaire (Morgeson & Humphrey, 2006)	Three items on <i>Planning Autonomy</i> , <i>Decision Autonomy</i> , and <i>Procedural Autonomy</i>	3–15; higher scores indicate greater autonomy	0.87
	Supervisor Support	Feedback Environment Scale (Steelman & Snell, 2004)	Five selected items and an additional custom item on general support	6–30; higher scores indicate more support	0.66
	Fatigue	Burnout Assessment Tool (BAT; Schaufeli, Desart & De Witte, 2020)	Full instrument of 12 items	12–60; higher scores indicate higher fatigue	0.91
	Well-being	Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES; Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004)	Six selected items	6–42; higher scores indicate better well-being	0.88
Physical well-being	Ergonomics	Work Design Questionnaire (Morgeson & Humphrey, 2006)	Scale <i>Ergonomics</i>	3–15; higher scores indicate higher satisfaction with ergonomics	0.07
	Physical Strain	Work Design Questionnaire (Morgeson & Humphrey, 2006)	Scale <i>Physical Task Demands</i>	3–15; higher scores indicate greater physical strain	0.97
Work organization	Physical Work Environment	Work Design Questionnaire (Morgeson & Humphrey, 2006)	Scale <i>Physical Work Environment</i>	5–25; higher scores indicate greater satisfaction with the work environment	0.68
	Material Use	Work Design Questionnaire (Morgeson & Humphrey, 2006)	Scale <i>Equipment Use</i>	3–15; higher scores indicate greater variety in equipment use	0.75
	Learning Opportunities	Learning and Development Survey (LDS; Tones & Pilay, 2008)	Three selected items	3–15; higher scores indicate more learning opportunities	0.68
	Work-Life Balance	SWING questionnaire (Geurts et al., 2005)	For selected items and an additional custom item on work-related contact during free time	5–20; higher scores indicate a more disrupted work-life balance	0.81
Technology	Attitude towards Technology	A brief screener based on the instrument of the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT2; Venkatesh, Thong & Xu, 2012)	Full instrument of 8 items	8–56; higher scores indicate a more positive attitude towards technology use	0.84

Note. Reliability: $\alpha < 0.5$ = low ; $0.5 \leq \alpha < 0.7$ = average ; $\alpha \geq 0.7$ = high

Data-analysis

Responses of the expert interviews were documented by the project partners in a data collection sheet, where they summarized the interviewee's answers, included exact quotes and any notable findings. Thematic analysis by two independent researchers identified key themes and subthemes, revealing common challenges, needs, and opportunities related to workability and technology integration.

Data from the co-creation sessions and diary booklets were similarly collected. Content analysis was conducted on the summaries of the sessions that the partners had documented in the data collection sheet. This analysis, carried out independently by two researchers, identified frequently mentioned tasks, energy-boosting and energy-draining aspects of work, as well as participants' views on workplace technology. The researchers critically reviewed each other's work to ensure consistency and enhance the reliability of the findings.

The online survey was administered via Qualtrics XM (2024), and data were analysed in SPSS (v29.0) by two independent researchers. Descriptive statistics provided an overview of responses. ANOVA-tests were used to assess differences between the four sectors, with Hochberg's GT2 post-hoc tests identifying where differences occurred. Sector-specific response distributions were analysed to highlight actionable insights. Open-ended responses about technology were analysed for recurring themes and concrete examples.

Finally, technologies identified across all methods were synthesized into distinct categories and mapped to specific workforce challenges. This ensures proposed technological interventions directly address the expressed needs of healthcare and welfare workers.

Results

Phase 1: Expert Interviews

A total of 38 (middle) management professionals participated in the interviews, spread across elderly care ($n = 9$), disability care ($n = 8$), childcare ($n = 8$), youth care ($n = 7$), and social enterprises for supported employment ($n = 6$).

Risk Factors

High workload. A majority of respondents (n = 29) reported high workload, primarily due to staff shortages (n = 14) and administrative burdens (n = 12). This challenge was especially pronounced in healthcare and welfare sectors. In elderly care, the lingering impact of the COVID-19 pandemic was particularly noticeable: “We haven’t had the chance to recover from the pandemic.” Participants indicated that absenteeism (n = 11) and turnover (n = 15) exacerbated staffing shortages. Administrative tasks (n = 9) also reduced time for direct care: “There are 101 small things to check off. We’re constantly on edge not to forget anything.”

Emotional strain. High emotional strain (n = 28) was prevalent, particularly among professionals working directly with clients. In youth care, the increasing complexity of client profiles, including severe behavioural issues and trauma, demanded significant emotional investment (n = 4). Workers in youth and disability care also dealt with client aggression (n = 5), leading to both safety risks and psychological stress. Communication with clients’ families was often difficult (n = 7), resulting in conflicts and a sense of underappreciation: “Group leaders sometimes feel underappreciated by management or families” (disability care); “Parents are becoming more demanding and less appreciative” (childcare).

Physical strain. Physical strain (n = 18) was especially severe for caregivers, nursing assistants, and logistical workers due to frequent lifting, long periods of standing, and other physically demanding tasks. In childcare, noise also contributes to physical stress (n = 2). Staff shortages sometimes led to situations where employees worked alone, increasing the physical workload and the risk of injuries: “Given that back pain is the leading cause of absenteeism, the high workload will inevitably lead to increased staff turnover.”

These findings are visually summarized in Figure 3, which provides an overview of the number of management professionals reporting a high workload, emotional strain or physical strain.

Figure 3. Perceived workload, emotional strain, and physical strain among management professionals

Note. Data reflect the number of management professionals ($n = 38$) who reported high levels of workload, emotional strain, or physical strain. Non-mention of a challenge does not necessarily indicate that it was not present.

Autonomy, task variation, and managerial support. According to managers, autonomy was influenced by personal preferences, team dynamics, and organizational structures ($n = 4$). Some employees preferred independence, while others sought guidance. Collaborative environments fostered autonomy, but strict protocols limited it. Task variation varied, some employees thrived on diversity, while others preferred structure ($n = 6$). However, they mentioned that too much variation led to stress. Managers reported a lack of support due to staff shortages ($n = 6$), leaving less time for team guidance: “If you don’t get feedback, it must be going well, but some people need more support than that.” Remote supervision in sectors like home care and youth care sometimes caused isolation, and communication gaps led to misunderstandings.

Workability Indicators

Learning opportunities. Managers across all sectors reported that workers were encouraged to participate in relevant training ($n = 23$), with input on course selection ($n = 7$). However, workplace pressure made it difficult to take time off for training, as it increased the workload for colleagues. In childcare, career progression was particularly limited, with few opportunities for advancement.

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

Work-life balance. The implementation of a disconnection policy was mentioned by one in five across sectors ($n = 7$), although its effectiveness varied. Managers were expected to be available outside working hours, and irregular or interrupted schedules, particularly in elderly and after-school childcare, posed challenges for employees with families ($n = 10$). They also indicated that they frequently had to cover for absent colleagues. In elderly care, communication during absences, such as a resident's death, was highly valued. Managers reported performing administrative tasks during personal time, further impacting their work-life balance. While work schedules were typically fixed in advance, they lacked flexibility. Attempts at self-scheduling were reported ineffective due to practical issues and varying employee preferences, with coordinators finding scheduling especially stressful.

Well-being. Managers across all sectors reported efforts to promote employee well-being through team-building activities and staff parties. However, team cohesion varied between organizations, and internal conflicts sometimes disrupted workplace dynamics. Sectors like elderly, disability, and youth care invested in relaxing programs, including sports facilities, yoga classes, and self-care initiatives. These sectors also employed mental coaches and internal psychologists to provide individual support.

Use of Technology

Healthcare and welfare professionals were generally open to technology, provided it added value without increasing workload. Resistance was more common among older employees ($n = 7$), those with limited Dutch proficiency, and those with lower digital literacy. Successful implementation required gradual introduction and adequate post-implementation support. Common concerns from managers included the fear of replacing personal contact, costs, sector-specific alignment and privacy issues (GDPR). While low-tech solutions such as height-adjustable beds were widely used, high-tech innovations were often underutilized due to limited training and funding. Managers across sectors emphasized the need for technological solutions to streamline administration. They advocated for integrated systems that allow various platforms to communicate, reducing inefficiencies and freeing workers to focus more on care delivery.

Phase 2: Co-Creation Sessions

In total, 46 healthcare and welfare professionals participated in seven co-creation sessions, spread across elderly care ($n = 18$), disability care ($n = 12$), childcare ($n = 13$), and youth care ($n = 3$). A separate session was organized for social enterprise for supported employments ($n = 6$). 35 participants completed the diary study, including nine who did not attend the co-creation sessions.

Motivations and Energy Levels from the Diary Study

In the diary study, 30 participants shared motivations for working in healthcare and welfare, with many expressing a passion for caregiving and helping others ($n = 22$). Others emphasized the meaningful contributions they made to individuals' lives ($n = 16$). Energy levels, measured at the end of the workweek, showed that frontline workers reported significantly lower energy ($M = 2.60$, $SD = 0.89$) compared to direct managers ($M = 3.86$, $SD = 0.55$), $t(12) = 2.92$, $p = 0.03$.

Burdensome Tasks, Energy Boosters and Energy Drainers

Participants identified various work-related stressors, including physical tasks (e.g., mobility assistance), administrative duties (e.g., documentation), and mentally demanding tasks (e.g., decision-making and crisis management). These challenges were particularly taxing for caregivers, coordinators, and administrative staff.

Key energy sources include teamwork, recognition, and work organization. Teamwork was valued across all sectors, with smaller teams in elderly care and strong connections in disability care. Recognition from residents, families, and colleagues also played a vital role. Work organization, with task variety and opportunities for learning, was appreciated, particularly in elderly and disability care. Professional development, especially in youth and disability care, was seen as a motivating factor.

Major energy drainers included administrative tasks, poor team dynamics, and communication challenges. Administrative tasks, such as paperwork and scheduling, took time away from direct care. Team challenges, such as poor collaboration and lack of responsibility, and external communication issues (e.g., difficult interactions with families and media) were also common stressors. Maintaining work-life balance was a challenge in all sectors, with staff sacrificing personal time for work-related tasks.

Use of Technology

The high cost of technology is a major barrier across sectors, along with the lack of system integration, leading to inefficiency. Workers expressed a desire for user-friendly technology that simplifies work and reduces repetitive tasks. There was also a need for ongoing support during and after technology implementation, with some workers resistant to change, particularly older workers. They highlighted the administrative burden as a major concern and saw technology as key to addressing it. They expressed a strong preference for connected and user-friendly digital systems to reduce duplication, save time, and support more efficient workflows.

Phase 3: Online Survey

526 individuals completed the survey. The demographic breakdown (Table 2) shows that most respondents were women, consistent with gender distributions in the sector. Age distribution was balanced across categories, and the majority worked full-time or over 50% of the time, with more than 10 years of experience. There was good representation from various sectors, although social enterprises for supported employment were not included. Demographics are similar to those registered for Belgian healthcare workers according to the Belgian statistical office (Statbel, 2020).

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

Table 2. Demographic characteristics of participated healthcare and welfare workers

Demographic data		Survey prevalences		Statbel healthcare workers ^a
		Prevalences (N)	Prevalences (%)	Prevalences (%)
Province	Limburg	120	22.81	13.24
	Antwerp	162	30.80	24.67
	Flemish Brabant	142	27.00	17.99
	East Flanders	85	16.16	23.87
	West Flanders	15	02.85	20.23
Gender	Man	91	17.30	21.40
	Woman	433	82.32	78.60
	Prefer not to say	2	0.38	/
	Other	0	0.00	/
Age	15-24 years	20	3.80	5.70
	25-34 years	146	27.76	27.47
	35-44 years	138	26.24	23.58
	45-54 years	136	25.86	22.03
	55-64 years	82	15.59	18.37
	65+ years	4	0.76	2.68
Living situation	Living alone	71	13.50	11.81
	Living with partner	127	24.14	21.85
	Living with partner and child(ren)	260	49.43	54.03
	Living with child(ren)	29	5.51	10.39
	Living with parent(s) ^b	33	6.27	1.90
	Living with other(s) ^b	4	0.76	/
Informal caregiver	Informal caregiver	72	13.69	/
	Lives with at least one person aged 65+	/	/	6.39
Sector	Elderly care	154	29.28	/
	Disability care	207	39.35	/
	Youth care	83	15.78	/
	Childcare	82	15.59	/
Working regime	Full-time	302	57.41	/
	Part-time: >50%	177	33.65	/
	Part-time: =< 50%	41	7.79	/
	Other ^c	6	1.14	/
Experience	0-5 years	103	19.58	/
	6-10 years	87	16.54	/
	>10 years	336	63.88	/
Total		526	100	

Note. ^a data from Statbel dated July 23, 2020, for care workers ; ^b Statbel does not provide separate data for living with parent(s) and living with other(s); ^c Under the working regime "other", there are four student workers, one volunteer, and one retiree.

Mental Well-being

Figure 4 shows the total scores across sectors on these three themes. Approximately one-third of care and welfare employees report high work pressure frequently. While 87.45% rarely or never struggle with work pace, 55.13% often or always face excessive workloads. Emotional strain is rarely experienced by most care and welfare workers. 82.13% rely on colleagues, and 74.14% find the work environment respectful. However, 40.88% struggle to detach from work. Care and welfare workers report sufficient task variation. 96.01% require diverse knowledge and skills for their work. Over half of care and welfare workers report sufficient autonomy. Most care and welfare workers feel adequately supported by their supervisors. 77.19% can rely on their supervisor, and 76.99% appreciate feedback.

Figure 4. Total scores across sectors: participant response percentages

Note. (a) Mental Well-Being; (b) Physical Well-Being; (c) Work Organization. In all scales, a more positive item response indicates a higher degree of the respective construct. However, this direction is reversed for the Emotional Strain and Work-Life Balance scales, in which all items are reverse scored; therefore, for these two scales, a more positive response reflects a lower level of the construct.

Figure 5 shows the reported high job satisfaction across sectors. 75.45% are enthusiastic about their work frequently, and 81.56% take pride in their work. Fatigue is rare for most

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

care and welfare workers. The average burnout risk score was 1.92 (BAT), indicating an average burnout risk. 70.91% feel mentally drained at work, 46.96% physically exhausted, and 48.48% rarely feel rested after work. No sector differences were found for work pressure, emotional strain, variation, support, job satisfaction, and fatigue; $F(3, 522) \leq 1.85$, $p \geq 0.14$. Significant sector differences were found for autonomy; $F(3, 522) = 3.10$, $p = 0.03$, with youth care workers experiencing more autonomy than elderly care workers (Figure 6a).

Figure 5. Job satisfaction across sectors

Note. A more positive item response indicates a higher degree of the respective construct.

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

Figure 6. Significant differences among the healthcare and welfare sectors

Note. Level of significance: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$. (a) The scales range from 3 to 15, with higher values indicating a greater sense of autonomy. (b) The scales range from 3 to 15, with higher values reflecting better perceived ergonomics. (c) The scales range from 3 to 15, with higher values indicating greater physical strain. (d) The scales range from 5 to 25, with higher values representing a more favourable work environment. (e) The scales range from 3 to 15, with higher values indicating the use of a greater quantity and/or complexity of materials.

Physical Well-being

While most care and welfare workers feel ergonomics are adequately considered, 23% report a lack of ergonomic support. Significant sector differences were found; $F(3, 522) = 5.70, p < 0.001$, with elderly care workers scoring higher than disability care workers (Figure 6b). Opinions on physical strain were divided, with 39.73% of employees reporting high physical strain. Significant sector differences were found; $F(3, 522) = 23.74, p <$

0.001. Physical strain was significantly higher in elderly care compared to other sectors, with disability care workers reporting more strain than youth care workers (Figure 6c).

Work Organization

Employees generally report a pleasant work environment, with excessive noise (42.4%) and uncomfortable temperature/humidity (38.22%) as the main disturbances. Around 30% report workplace accident risks. About half of them report working with diverse tools (48.10%) and find them neither complex (67.68%) nor time-consuming (67.31%). Most employees have access to training opportunities (90.49%) and would participate if offered (85.74%). Over 20% of employees report frequent or constant disruption of work-life balance. No sector differences were found for learning opportunities and work-life balance; $F(3, 522) \leq 1.94, p \geq 0.12$. Significant sector differences were found for work environment; $F(3, 522) = 4.35, p = 0.005$, with childcare scoring significantly higher than disability care (Figure 6d) and materials; $F(3, 522) = 6.92, p < 0.001$, particularly between elderly care, childcare, and youth care, with elderly care workers reporting more varied or complex material use (Figure 6e).

Attitudes Toward Technology

Over half of healthcare and welfare workers (62.07%) are open to using technology (Figure 7). Three-quarters find technology usage somewhat enjoyable (76.24%) and would likely use it in the future (73.77%). No sector differences were found; $F(3, 522) = 0.88, p = 0.45$.

Figure 7. Total scores across sectors on technology acceptance: participant response percentages

Note. A more positive item response indicates a higher degree of Technology Acceptance.

Phase 4: Synthesizing Technology Solutions

The data collected through the three methods revealed a wide array of care technologies, which were categorized into six key areas, each addressing specific functions and needs within the care environment (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Types of care technologies

The first category, (1) *activating care technologies*, is intended to support patients in daily activities and reduce the workload of care providers. An example identified by healthcare professionals is an "Magic Table" that facilitates cognitive and physical stimulation through games or exercises. (2) *Relaxing care technologies* aim to promote mental relaxation and emotional well-being for both patients and care providers, such as wellbeing-apps or a "sensory stimulation tent". (3) *Ergonomic care technologies*, e.g. sliding sheets and mobile hoists, assist caregivers in performing physically demanding tasks, reducing strain and injury risks. These are commonly used for patient handling, improving comfort for both workers and patients. (4) *Assistive care technologies* improve caregiving efficiency by providing tools for various tasks, examples like alarm systems

and wandering detection enhance patient safety by alerting workers to risks and enabling timely intervention. (5) *Administrative support tools* streamline non-care-related tasks like scheduling and documentation. These tools aim to enhance operational efficiency and communication within care teams. However, healthcare professionals have expressed concerns about challenges in integrating these tools into existing workflows. (6) *Educational support tools*, such as learning apps or online platforms, provide opportunities for continuous learning in the workplace. These technologies enable care professionals to acquire new skills and knowledge while working.

Conclusion and Discussion

It is important to involve healthcare and welfare professionals in the selection of technological solutions to improve adoption and effectiveness in combatting workplace challenges. This study aimed to explore the role of technology in supporting professionals in various care sectors, specifically elderly care, disability care, youth care, childcare, and social enterprises for supported employment, by addressing challenges related to mental and physical well-being, and work organization. The participatory living lab approach played a crucial role in ensuring that the technologies identified were aligned with the real-world needs of healthcare professionals. By involving a diverse group of workers in the development process, the study was able to identify care technology categories that are both relevant and practical for addressing their challenges.

An important strength of this study lies in the diversity of care sectors included. By bringing together professionals from multiple domains, each with their own unique challenges, the study fostered cross-sectoral learning. Professionals gained insights into each other's working conditions, allowing them to reflect on shared and sector-specific barriers. This also revealed that the adoption of technology progresses at different speeds across sectors, depending on factors such as organizational maturity, workforce demographics, and prior exposure to technological solutions. Future projects can tailor their approaches to these factors, ensuring that implementation strategies fit the specific context of each care setting.

The results highlighted the significant challenges faced by healthcare workers in Flanders, including high levels of mental strain, physical strain, and the need for improved work organization, which is consistent with previous research (Vandenbroeck et al. 2017; SERV, 2024; De Vries et al., 2023; Hudays et al. 2024). These challenges were often compounded by high workloads, administrative burdens, and the increasing complexity of client profiles. Despite these difficulties, participants expressed a positive attitude

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures:

Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

toward technology, particularly when it is tailored to address their specific needs in mental health, physical health, and work organization.

This study was able to document challenges and match them with technological solutions, as can be seen in Figure 9. One of the key findings was the identification of six categories of care technology that could potentially alleviate these challenges: activating care technology, relaxing care technology, ergonomic care technology, assistive care technology, administrative support tools, and educational support tools. Each of these technologies addresses specific aspects of workability, as identified through the data collection process.

Figure 9. Mapping care technologies to identified challenges

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

Activating and relaxing care technologies were identified as potential solutions for alleviating emotional and mental strain for both patients and healthcare workers. These technologies may have the potential to enhance emotional well-being and reduce the emotional exhaustion reported by participants. Ergonomic care technologies are crucial for reducing the physical strain on healthcare workers during patient handling. These technologies not only help prevent injuries but also improve comfort and safety for both workers and patients, which is particularly important given the high physical demands of healthcare work. Assistive care technology improves efficiency by supporting care professionals in their tasks. Also, the study revealed a high demand for administrative support tools to alleviate the burden of non-care-related tasks. Healthcare professionals frequently reported dissatisfaction with existing administrative tools, citing issues such as inefficiency, incompatibility with existing systems, and a lack of user-friendliness. Addressing these issues by investing in more effective and compatible administrative technologies could reduce the time spent on administrative duties, allowing healthcare professionals to focus more on direct patient care. Furthermore, educational support tools were identified as a promising solution for addressing the ongoing need for professional development and training. Although numerous training opportunities are available, time constraints often limit their effectiveness. The integration of educational technologies into the workplace could provide professionals with opportunities for continuous learning without adding further time pressure.

Beyond the concrete technology categories, this study also highlights the importance of bridging the gap between frontline care workers and management profiles. Both groups were involved in the process, allowing for a more nuanced understanding of where priorities align and where tensions exist, for example, between operational challenges and strategic objectives. This holistic perspective is crucial for ensuring that technological innovations are both workable for workers and feasible from an organizational standpoint.

Throughout the study, participatory activities such as interviews, co-creation sessions, and the survey not only collected data but also empowered care professionals to reflect on their own roles in technology adoption. Participants considered the balance between human-centered care and technological support, reflecting on themes such as dehumanization versus relief through automation. This reflective process supports more sustainable adoption because it ensures that technology implementation is not imposed from above but emerges from the perspectives and concerns of those who will ultimately use it.

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

Additionally, this study contributes to advancing care innovation by applying a participatory approach that aligns with both the Quadruple and Quintuple Helix innovation models (Carayannis, Barth, & Campbell, 2012). The Quadruple Helix highlights collaboration among four key actors: academia, industry, government, and civil society. In this project, this is reflected through the active involvement of government representatives and large care organizations in the steering and advisory groups. Furthermore, technology providers are engaged in organizing demonstration sessions and pilot projects, while the project consortium includes multiple universities of applied sciences and knowledge institutions. This multi-stakeholder collaboration ensures that technological solutions are selected with broad input, increasing their relevance and acceptance within healthcare practice. The Quintuple Helix framework extends this approach by incorporating the environment and broader societal context as a fifth dimension. This is particularly important in the healthcare sector, where sustainability and worker well-being are central concerns. By situating innovation within this wider societal and environmental framework, the study emphasizes not only technological advancement but also the sustainable and human-centered implementation of technology in care and welfare settings. This research demonstrates how cross-sector collaboration and iterative Living Lab processes can effectively tackle complex healthcare challenges, leading to solutions that are both context-sensitive and sustainable.

While the findings indicate that healthcare workers in Flanders are generally open to adopting technology, several barriers must be overcome to ensure successful implementation. These barriers include cost, lack of training, time constraints, and resistance to change. As highlighted in this study, integrating new technologies into existing workflows can be challenging, particularly for older workers or those with limited proficiency in the local language. These factors underscore the need for targeted strategies that consider the diverse needs of healthcare workers, ensuring that technology adoption is both feasible and beneficial. These findings are consistent with previous research (Turner et al., 2021; Robertson et al., 2024; Garcia et al., 2024). A key next step is the practical application of these findings in care settings. In the follow-up phases of this project, demonstration sessions and pilot projects will be organized to test and refine the selected technologies in real work environments. These activities will allow care professionals and organizations to experiment with solutions, adapt them to their needs, and gradually integrate them into daily practice. Based on the insights from these phases, an implementation guide will be developed to support care and welfare organizations in introducing technology in a sustainable and context-sensitive way. This

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures:

Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

guide will provide practical recommendations on selecting, implementing, and embedding technology to improve workability and well-being in the sector.

However, the relatively small sample size from the youth care sector may have limited the breadth of insights from this group. Future research could benefit from a larger, more diverse sample to gain a broader understanding of the challenges and technology needs across various healthcare settings. Another limitation of this study is that it was conducted exclusively with Dutch-speaking care workers. As the care sector in Flanders and beyond increasingly employs workers from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds, future research should explore how non-Dutch-speaking newcomers experience and navigate the workplace. This would help to develop more inclusive support systems and technologies tailored to a broader range of care professionals. Additionally, while social enterprises for supported employments were included in the qualitative phase, they were not represented in the quantitative data. Although the proposed technologies appear promising for these settings, further research is needed to assess their relevance and impact within this specific context.

In conclusion, this study indicates the potential for technology to enhance the workability of healthcare workers by addressing key challenges related to emotional and physical strain, and work organization. Importantly, the results suggest that this potential does not require radical changes to existing care models, but rather incremental improvements aligned with current practices and mindsets. By adopting activating, relaxing, ergonomic, assistive, administrative, and educational technologies, employee satisfaction and workplace efficiency could be improved. However, the successful implementation of these technologies will require overcoming barriers such as cost, training, and resistance to change. Therefore, a collaborative (living lab) approach that involves healthcare professionals, managers, and technology providers is essential for ensuring the successful adoption of these tools in healthcare settings. Further research is needed to evaluate the long-term impact of these technologies on both healthcare workers' well-being and the quality of patient care, as well as to explore the potential for broader implementation across different healthcare sectors.

References

1. A'aqoulah, A., Kuyini, A. B., & Albalas, S. (2022). Exploring the Gap Between Patients' Expectations and Perceptions of Healthcare Service Quality. *Patient Preference and Adherence*, 16, 1295–1305. <https://doi.org/10.2147/PPA.S360852>
2. Barber, S., Otis, M., Greenfield, G., Razzaq, N., Solanki, D., Norton, J., Richardson, S., & Hayhoe, B. W. J. (2023). Improving multidisciplinary team working to support integrated care for people with frailty amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Integrated Care*, 23(2), 23. <https://doi.org/10.5334/ijic.7022>
3. Carayannis, E. G., Barth, T. D., & Campbell, D. F. (2012). The Quintuple Helix innovation model: global warming as a challenge and driver for innovation. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 1(1), 2. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2192-5372-1-2>
4. Carlsen, B., & Glenton, C. (2011). What about N? A methodological study of sample-size reporting in focus group studies. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2288-11-26>
5. Czypionka, T., Kraus, M., Reiss, M., & Baltaxe, E. (2020). The future of integrated care: A scoping review of the literature. *Health Policy*, 124(12), 1273–1280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthpol.2020.09.003>
6. De Marez, L., Georges, A., Sevenhant, R., & Devos, E. (2025). imec.digimeter 2024: Digitale trends in Vlaanderen. imec. <https://www.imec.be/sites/default/files/2025-03/imec.digimeter-2024-rapport.pdf>
7. De Vries, N., Boone, A., Godderis, L., Bouman, J., Szemik, S., Matranga, D., & De Winter, P. (2023). The Race to Retain Healthcare Workers: A Systematic Review on Factors that Impact Retention of Nurses and Physicians in Hospitals. *INQUIRY the Journal of Health Care Organization Provision and Financing*, 60. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00469580231159318>
8. De Witte, N. A., De Cat, A., Vandenhoudt, H., Vermeylen, S., Van Der Auwera, V., Broeckx, L., & Adriaensen, I. (2024). Sustainable user involvement: Building a user community and fostering high-quality research. In *De Gruyter eBooks* (pp. 35–60). <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783111241036-003>
9. Familiezorg. (2008, 25 januari). Vragenlijst en begeleidende brief Knipperlichtmeter: https://cdn.nimbu.io/s/596mlap/channelentries/hcylrd1/files/300709131324_vragenlijst-en-begeleidende-brief-knipperlichtmeter%20_2_%20_10_.pdf
10. Freilich, J., Wiking, E., Nilsson, G. H., & Olsson, C. (2019). Patients' ideas, concerns, expectations and satisfaction in primary health care – a questionnaire study of patients and health care professionals' perspectives. *Scandinavian Journal of Primary Health Care*, 37(4), 468–475. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02813432.2019.1684430>
11. Garcia, M. B., Arif, Y. M., Khlaif, Z. N., Zhu, M., De Almeida, R. P. P., De Almeida, R. S., & Masters, K. (2024). Effective integration of artificial intelligence in medical education. In *Advances in healthcare information systems and administration book series* (pp. 1–19). <https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3693-3661-8.ch001>
12. Geurts, S. A. E., Taris, T. W., Kompier, M. A. J., Dijkers, J. S. E., Van Hooff, M. L. M., & Kinnunen, U. M. (2005). Work-home interaction from a work psychological perspective: Development and validation of a new questionnaire, the SWING. *Work & Stress*, 19(4), 319–339.
13. Guest, G., Namey, E., & McKenna, K. (2016). How many focus groups are enough? Building an evidence base for nonprobability sample sizes. *Field Methods*, 29(1), 3–22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1525822x16639015>
14. Hudays, A., Gary, F., Voss, J. G., Arishi, A., Alfar, Z. A., Algodimi, A. M., & Fitzpatrick, J. J. (2024). Factors Influencing Job Satisfaction among Mental Health Nurses: A Systematic Review. *Healthcare*, 12(20), 2040. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare12202040>
15. Kingston, A., Comas-Herrera, A., & Jagger, C. (2018). Forecasting the care needs of the older population in England over the next 20 years: estimates from the Population Ageing and Care Simulation (PACSim) modelling study. *The Lancet Public Health*, 3(9), e447–e455. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2468-2667\(18\)30118-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2468-2667(18)30118-x)

16. Kroezen, M., Dussault, G., Craveiro, I., Dieleman, M., Jansen, C., Buchan, J., Barriball, L., Rafferty, A. M., Bremner, J., & Sermeus, W. (2015b). Recruitment and retention of health professionals across Europe: A literature review and multiple case study research. *Health Policy*, 119(12), 1517–1528. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthpol.2015.08.003>
17. Marć, M., Bartosiewicz, A., Burzyńska, J., Chmiel, Z., & Januszewicz, P. (2018). A nursing shortage – a prospect of global and local policies. *International Nursing Review*, 66(1), 9–16. <https://doi.org/10.1111/inr.12473>
18. Morgeson, F. P., & Humphrey, S. E. (2006). The Work Design Questionnaire (WDQ): Developing and validating a comprehensive measure for assessing job design and the nature of work. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 91(6), 1321–1339. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.91.6.1321>
19. Morse, J. M. (2000). Determining sample size. *Qualitative Health Research*, 10(1), 3–5. <https://doi.org/10.1177/104973200129118183>
20. Robertson, S. T., Brauer, S. G., Burton-Jones, A., Grimley, R. S., & Rosbergen, I. C. (2024). From use, value and user-centered design to context: A mixed methods analysis of a hospital electronic medical record enhancement. *Digital Health*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20552076241279208>
21. Saadat, S., Daroukolaei, M. K., Qorbani, M., Hemmat, A., & Hariri, S. (2025). Enhancing Clinical Documentation with AI: Reducing Errors, Improving Interoperability, and Supporting Real-Time Notetaking. *InfoScience Trends*, 2(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.61186/ist.202502.01.01>
22. Schaufeli, W. B., & Bakker, A. B. (2004). Job demands, job resources, and their relationship with burnout and engagement: a multi-sample study. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 25(3), 293–315. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.248>
23. Schaufeli, W. B., Desart, S., & De Witte, H. (2020). Burnout Assessment Tool (BAT)—Development, Validity, and Reliability. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(24), 9495. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17249495>
24. Shemtob, L., Asanati, K., Pahl, N., & Majeed, A. (2023). What needs to be done to address staffing shortages in health and social care? *British Journal of General Practice*, 73(728), 102–103. <https://doi.org/10.3399/bjgp23x732045>
25. Sociaal-Economische Raad van Vlaanderen (SERV). (2024). Werkbaar werk in de zorg- en welzijnssector 2023: Sectorale analyse op de Vlaamse werkbaarheidsmonitor 2004–2023.
26. Steelman, L. A., Levy, P. E., & Snell, A. F. (2004). The feedback Environment scale: construct definition, measurement, and validation. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 64(1), 165–184. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013164403258440>
27. Stichting Innovatie & Arbeid. https://www.serv.be/sites/default/files/documenten/SERV_20240703_WBM2023_WNS_zorg_StIA_RAP.pdf
28. Suh, C., & Punnett, L. (2022). High emotional demands at work and poor mental health in Client-Facing workers. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(12), 7530. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19127530>
29. Tones, M. & Pillay, H. (2008). Further evaluation of the learning and development survey: psychometric properties. *Australian Journal of Educational and Developmental Psychology*, 8, 85–97.
30. Turner, S., Botero-Tovar, N., Herrera, M. A., Kuhlmann, J. P. B., Ortiz, F., Ramírez, J. C., & Maldonado, L. F. (2021). Systematic review of experiences and perceptions of key actors and organisations at multiple levels within health systems internationally in responding to COVID-19. *Implementation Science*, 16(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13012-021-01114-2>
31. Vandenbroeck, S., Van Gerven, E., De Witte, H., Vanhaecht, K., & Godderis, L. (2017). Burnout in Belgian physicians and nurses. *Occupational Medicine*, 67(7), 546–554. <https://doi.org/10.1093/occmed/kqx126>
32. VDAB. (2024). Knelpuntberoepen in Vlaanderen 2025. In *Knelpuntberoepen in Vlaanderen (2025th ed.)*. <https://www.vdab.be/sites/default/files/media/files/Knelpuntberoepen2025.pdf>
33. Venkatesh, V., Thong, J. Y. L., & Xu, X. (2012). Consumer acceptance and use of information technology: Extending the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology. *MIS Quarterly: Management Information Systems*, 36(1), 157–178. <https://doi.org/10.2307/41410412>

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

34. Verzorgend personeel | Statbel. (2020b, July 23). <https://statbel.fgov.be/nl/themas/datalab/verzorgend-personeel>
35. Werkdruk: wat is het en hoe kun je het verlagen? (n.d.). FNV. <https://www.fnv.nl/werk-inkomen/veilig-gezond-werken/werkdruk>
36. World Health Organization. (2016). Working for health and growth: Investing in the health workforce. Report of the High-Level Commission on Health Employment and Economic Growth. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241511308>
37. Zorginstituut Nederland. (2024). Onderzoek naar beoordeling van digitale zorgtechnologieën. <https://www.zorginstituutnederland.nl/publicaties/rapport/2024/05/27/onderzoek-beoordeling-van-digitale-zorgtechnologieen>Zorginstituut Nederland+6
38. Zorgnet-Icuro. (2024, 9 april). Managen van het verwachtingspatroon. Zorgnet-Icuro. <https://www.zorgneticuro.be/verkiezingen-2024-hoe-houden-we-onze-zorg-houdbaar/09-managen-van-het-verwachtingspatroon>